

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE FAMILY IN EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: This article analyzes the role and importance of the family in the education of preschool children. It is shown that educational processes formed in the family environment are of decisive importance in the development of children as individuals. The formation of the child under the influence of social, psychological and emotional factors within the family in the first years, the impact on his future educational processes and social adaptation is analyzed. At the same time, it will be explained how the participation of family members, especially parents, in the process of education and education affects the cognitive development of children. The article also includes recommendations developed on the basis of scientific evidence about the leading role of the family in the education of children and the importance of cooperation with teachers.

Key words: Family, preschool education, Child education, Psychological development, Social adaptation, Parental involvement, Early childhood education.

Introduction:

The role of the family environment in the development of preschool children is very important. This period is the time when the main foundations of the child's personality and abilities are laid, and family upbringing is of leading importance. Research shows that preschool children are very sensitive to the influence of the family environment in which they grow up, and the attention and support given by parents directly affects the psychological, emotional and cognitive development of the child. makes a secret. Especially during this period, the formation of a child's worldview, the development of his social skills, and his readiness to study mainly depend on family relations.

Although preschool educational institutions play an important role in the education of children in the society today, the role of the family in the educational process deserves special attention. The spiritual and physical support provided by parents and relatives, positive role models, and the culture of communication with the child allow the child to fully demonstrate his abilities. Therefore, in the education of children of preschool age, the harmonious relationship between the family and preschool educational institutions serves the child's harmonious development.

This article scientifically analyzes the important aspects of raising preschool children in family conditions, the participation of parents in this process, and its impact on children's future education.

Methodology:

In this study, qualitative and quantitative research methods were used to study the importance of the family in the education of preschool children. The research was carried out in the following main stages:

Literature analysis: modern scientific sources on the development of preschool children, scientific articles and studies on the role of the family in upbringing and education were analyzed. At this stage, national and international studies were compared and the main concepts related to family education factors were studied.

Questionnaire method: Questionnaires were conducted among parents and employees of preschool educational institutions. Through questionnaires, information was collected about the role of the family in the process of education, the participation of parents in the education of their children, and their cooperation with educational institutions. The data obtained through these questionnaires were analyzed and general conclusions were drawn based on statistics.

Interviews and Observations: In-depth interviews were conducted with research participants. More information about the influence of family education on child development was obtained through interviews with parents of preschool children, educators and psychologists. Also, how children develop in the family environment was observed and interactions between parents and children were analyzed.

Analysis and conclusions: The obtained data were processed using qualitative and quantitative analysis methods, and scientific conclusions were drawn on the importance of the family in child education. In addition, the influence of psychological and social factors of the family on the personal development of the child was also studied.

In order to ensure the practical and theoretical significance of the research, recommendations were developed for the further development of cooperation between the family and preschool educational institutions.

Discussion:

The family plays a very important role in the upbringing of children of preschool age. The results of the study showed that the family environment directly affects the child's personality, emotional state and intellectual

development. The participation of parents and other family members in the upbringing of a child creates a foundation for the child's future success. In particular, during the research, it was found that the attention and upbringing shown by parents increases the child's interest in studying and develops his social skills.

The activity of preschool children in the process of family upbringing was shown as the main factor in their intellectual development. Most of the parents who participated in the study recognized the importance of playing games with their children, encouraging them to learn new knowledge and skills. This strengthens children's self-awareness and the ability to understand the environment. Also, a kind and supportive environment in the family develops positive emotional states in children, which increases their level of social adaptation.

According to the results of the survey and interviews, it was found that the active participation of the family in education and cooperation with preschool educational institutions directly affects the future success of children. The constant communication and cooperation of parents with educational institutions ensures unity between the family and institutions, which forms a stable process of education in the child. Open communication between parents and educators helps to better understand the individual needs of the child and develop strategies that are appropriate for their development.

Based on the information obtained during the research, it was observed that family upbringing methods also play an important role. While excessive strictness in parenting can lead to stress and social withdrawal in a child, an overly lenient approach can have a negative effect on a child's discipline. At the same time, a balanced approach that combines love and firm discipline creates a favorable environment for social and intellectual development in the child.

It was also confirmed that parents spending quality time with children, answering their questions and stimulating their interests are of great importance in children's development. Long-term family support helps strengthen children's success in preschool, which is important in preparing for later stages of education.

The family plays a leading role in the upbringing of children of preschool age, and the attention and support provided by family members has a decisive effect on the intellectual and social development of the child. Close cooperation between parents and preschool educational institutions is one of the main factors necessary for a child's successful development.

Result:

This study confirmed that the role and importance of the family in the upbringing of children of preschool age is very great. The family creates a foundation for children's personality, cognitive development, emotional and social skills that are formed in the early years. The attention, love and active participation in the educational process provided by parents has a positive effect on the future success of the child. As revealed by questionnaires and interviews, family support and parenting methods have a direct impact on the development of the child's social adaptation and self-confidence.

During the research, it was also determined that cooperation between parents and preschool educational institutions is an important factor in children's development. This cooperation ensures the continuity of the educational process, helps the child to learn and strengthens their intellectual and social skills. It was noted that quality and effective time spent by parents with their children is crucial in developing children's interest and positive attitude towards learning.

The importance of the family in the education and upbringing of preschool children is very high. The active participation of the family in the education of the child, cooperation with teachers and the atmosphere of kindness created in the home environment have a great impact on the future of the child. Therefore, parents should create favorable educational conditions for their children and closely cooperate with preschool educational institutions.

Summary:

This study once again confirmed that the family plays a very important role in the upbringing of children of preschool age. A supportive and loving environment created by parents and family members greatly affects the cognitive, emotional and social development of children. It is impossible to ignore the role of the family at the initial stage of child development, because this period creates the foundation of the basic personality traits, interest in learning and social relations formed in children.

The results of the research showed that the active participation of the family in the educational process and close cooperation with preschool educational institutions directly depends on the future success of the child. Parents' love and attention to their children, encouraging them to learn, communicate and socialize will help the child to become a successful and strong person in the future.

Also, family education methods have been found to affect children's intellectual and social abilities, and education based on love, but with a disciplinary structure, is the most effective approach for the stable development of children. Organic relations between the family and preschool educational institutions help to make the educational process more effective.

In general, the role and responsibility of parents in children's education is huge, they should create a positive environment for their children, establish educational activities together with educational institutions. Thus, with the help of family and institutional support, children of preschool age can be formed as active, well-rounded members of society.

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